

APPLICATIONS OF STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING USING FIBER OPTIC SENSORS

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SUMMARY

Due to their many advantages, fiber optic sensors are quite useful for structural health monitoring. Despite of these advantages, there were still some problems to overcome for real applications. In this paper, some trials to improve FBG sensor and system such as enhancing sensor strength, stabilizing sensor system and several applied cases are introduced.

Keywords: fiber optic sensors, structural health monitoring, FBG sensors

INTRODUCTION

Fiber optic sensors have many advantages such as ease of embedding, flexible sensor size, wide temperature range, high sensitivity and etc[1]. Thus, fiber optic sensors have been introduced into many composite structures. Especially, FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) strain sensors have noticeable attractions due to multiplexing capability, linear response and absolute measurement [2]. However, the use of FBG sensors is limited by their simultaneous dependence on strain and temperature, directional sensitivity variation, weakened sensor head due to fabrication process, etc [3, 4]. In case of detecting high frequency signals, multiplexing capability is worse and conversely, most multiplexed FBG systems have low frequency ranges. And the sensitivity fadeout problem in the intensity demodulation method is another issue for FBG vibration sensor system. To overcome sensitivity fadeout problems, some passively controlled systems for a single-head FBG sensors system were suggested but do not guarantee uniform sensitivity [5]. And to measure internal and external strains of the composite pressure vessels in real time, the mechanical failure of FBG sensors or optical fiber and the spectral distortion in reflected signals have to be overcome [6]. Thus, in order to implement FBG sensors to real structures, much attention has been paid to overcome these limitations.

The research fields covered in this paper are as follows: simultaneous monitoring of strain and temperature embedded into composites using strength enhanced FBG sensors, impact monitoring of smart composites using stabilized FBG sensor system, and structural health monitoring of composite pressure vessels using FBG sensors. To enhance the mechanical strength of FBGs, several factors (hydrogen loading treatment, stripping jacket of optical fiber, UV laser condition, etc) have been tested. For discrimination of strain and temperature, a suitable sensor which is formed by two FBGs was designed. These FBGs are written in optical fibers with two Bragg gratings

having peak wavelengths around 1550 nm of similar strain sensitivity but different response to temperature. And a novel stabilized FBG vibration sensor system in a high frequency range was developed. This system consists of a stabilization controlling system and a tunable FFP (fiber Fabry-Perot) filter with narrow FSR (free spectral range) for multiplexing demodulator[7]. In case of application of FBGs to composite pressure vessels, some improvements for better sensors (mechanical strength, coating material and thickness, etc), better setups (protection of ingress/egress sections, alignment, etc) and better systems (signal distortion) were carried out.

SIMULTANEOUS MONITORING OF STRAIN AND TEMPERATURE

FBG Sensor Design for Simultaneous Monitoring

The wavelength changes of FBG sensors are coupled by mechanical strain and thermal strain. Temperature changes induce two effects on the FBG parameters. The thermal elongation of the fiber modifies the grating period Λ and the thermo-optic effects modify the refractive index functions (Δn_{ac} , Δn_{dc}). In the same manner, an applied stress on the fiber will lead to a geometric effect on the grating period and a refractive index change due to the photoelastic effect. Both effects can coexist and the Bragg wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_b$ can be expressed as

$$\Delta\lambda_B = 2 \left[\left(\Lambda \frac{\partial n_{eff}}{\partial L} + n_{eff} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial L} \right) \Delta L + \left(\Lambda \frac{\partial n_{eff}}{\partial T} + n_{eff} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial T} \right) \Delta T \right] \quad (1)$$

where L represent the grating length and T the temperature. And the relative Bragg wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_B/\lambda_B$ can be expressed by using the temperature sensitivity $K_T = \alpha + \xi$ and the strain sensitivity $K_\varepsilon = 1 - p_e$.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = K_T \Delta T + K_\varepsilon \Delta \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be converted to matrix form, which can be solved to obtain simultaneously the temperature change and strain[8].

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta T \\ \varepsilon \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{T1} & K_{\varepsilon1} \\ K_{T2} & K_{\varepsilon2} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B1}}{\lambda_{B1}} \\ \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B2}}{\lambda_{B2}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) can be written in vector form as $x = K^{-1}y$. Using this expression, the efficiency of discrimination the temperature and the strain contribution can be evaluated. The relative error δx in temperature and strain is related to the Bragg wavelength change vector δy as follows

$$\frac{\|\delta x\|}{\|x\|} \leq C(K) \frac{\|\delta y\|}{\|y\|} \quad (4)$$

where $C(K) = \|K\| \|K^{-1}\|$ is the condition number of the matrix of coefficient K . In order to reduce the error in the simultaneous evaluation of strain and temperature, a small condition number is desired.

Several methods have been reported to discriminate between temperature and strain[9]. As a result of evaluation using multiplexing, simplicity of the system, easiness to embed and condition number, method using FBGs with spliced different fibers is effective in use. Thus we proposed a sensor design using this method and tried to find best combination of different co-dopant fibers with better condition number.

A 193 nm excimer laser and the phase mask technique were used to inscribe 7 mm long Bragg gratings in GeO_2 , B_2O_3 , Er and Sn co-doped fibers, and these FBGs were tested with temperature sensitivity. The measured temperature sensitivity has nonlinear tendency and linear and 2nd regression fit were used. To remove the polarization dependent effects, polarization scrambler was used. Finally, FBGs in Cabloptic germane-silicate fiber with 22 mol% GeO_2 and in a Fibercore PS1500 germanium-boron co-doped fiber were selected for new sensing element. Temperature and strain sensitivities were $K_{T1} = 9.20 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, $K_{T2} = 11.58 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, $K_{\epsilon1} = 1.18 \text{ pm}/\mu\epsilon$ and $K_{\epsilon2} = 1.16 \text{ pm}/\mu\epsilon$, respectively. These sensitivities lead to a well-conditioned matrix solution for the temperature and strain discrimination. Fig. 1 shows the temperature sensitivities with gratings of G22 and PS1500 fiber.

Figure 1. Temperature sensitivity with gratings in G22 and PS1500 fiber.

Strength Enhanced FBG Sensors

In order to apply FBG sensors as reliable sensors in the commercial field, the reliability of the mechanical strength should be confirmed and the maximum strain should surpass the fracture strain of the host structure to measure the measurands until the host structures fail. Thus, several factors influencing the mechanical strength of FBGs have been tested. The negligible mechanical strength degradation of the chemical stripping technique and H₂ loading treatment was verified. In order to reduce damaged regions, the UV laser beam width exposed on the fiber was controlled to 60 μm. As a result, the mechanical strength was increased by 39%. Also experiments showed that increasing both the pulse fluence and total irradiated dose induced mechanical strength degradation. Finally, FBGs with high reflectivity were fabricated and showed sufficiently high mechanical strength. The mean failure strength of FBGs having a 90% reflectivity and 10 mm gauge length was 1.83±0.14 GPa.

IMPACT MONITORING USING STABILIZED FBG SENSOR SYSTEM

Stabilized FBG ultrasonic sensor system

A multiplexing scheme for a high-speed demodulation is necessary to improve the system efficiency for the construction of the multipoint AE sensing array of impact damage assessment system for a large structure. In order to develop a demodulation system of the FBG interrogator, an intensity demodulator using a FFP filter was modified by adopting an active stabilization control system to avoid sensitivity fadeout problems and to maintain the maximum sensitivity of the FBG vibration sensors. Moreover, a high frequency detectable multiplexing method was developed using the FFP filter with a narrow FSR (FSR=23.80 nm, spectral width=0.12 nm), which can demodulate the input signals of two FBG sensors simultaneously without the loss of measurable frequency range. Fig. 2 shows the diagram of stabilization controlled FBG sensor system. Between 1530 nm and 1560 nm range, two FBG sensors can be simultaneously demodulated using this sensor system.

Figure 2. Closed-loop stabilization controlled FBG sensor system.

In order to verify the performance of the proposed FBG vibration sensor system, the sensitivity and frequency response of the FBG sensor system were measured. From the

sensitivity measurement test, averaged sensitivity of the FBG vibration sensor is measured to be $2.56 \text{ n}\epsilon_{\text{rms}} / \sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ and FBG showed more flat frequency response than PZT sensor over a 20 kHz ~ 500 kHz range as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Frequency response of FBG and PZT sensors.

Finally, multi-points vibration tests using in-line FBG sensors were conducted to validate the multiplexing performance of the FBG system. From results of the multiplexing vibration test, the two FBG signals were interrogated by the single FFP filter and separated by the CWDM coupler, and sharp peaks of the oscillation frequencies up to 200 kHz, ultrasonic range (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Power spectra and vibration signal measured by FBG at 200 kHz vibration.

Those experiments showed that the proposed FBG vibration sensor system shows sufficient performance as an ultrasonic AE sensor and the FFP filter with narrow FSR can demodulate two of FBGs simultaneously without diminishing the detectable frequency range. And the sensitivity maintenance performance test was carried out in a

temperature-changing environment of a thermal chamber. Compared to the results from uncontrolled case, the SNR and sensitivity of 52.43 dB and $2.5 n\varepsilon_{rms} / \sqrt{Hz}$ could be maintained in the stabilization-controlled case.

Monitoring of impact damage on composite laminates using FBG sensors

To use FBG sensors to diagnosis the impact damage on composite laminates, the signal processing method that considers the directional sensitivity of an FBG sensor and attenuation property of AE signals on composites must be developed. In order to confirm the feasibility of the proposed damage assessment method and to find the signal characteristics of impact induced AE as the different propagation distance and incident angle to an FBG sensor, an impact test using the FBG sensors was performed. From the results, intensity of the AE signal decreases with the propagation length due to the signal attenuation property of composite materials, and the FBG sensor cannot detect the firstly reached leading wave anymore over 60° of the incident angle. Therefore, it can be concluded that it is possible to misjudge the damage condition by using only the intensity level of AE signals as a damage criterion of AE sensing method.

Thus, to quantify the variation of frequency characteristics of AE signals, sharing portions of the wavelet details were compared. In case of the D_4^{IM} wavelet detail component, the sharing portion grows from 43 % to 53 % showing the increment of 10 % if a structural damage occurs (Fig. 5). The wavelet details of AE signal show the consistent tendency in sharing portion regardless of the propagation length and incident angle in composites medium. From the above experiment, it can be concluded that this novel damage assessment method using the shared portion change in frequency domain is a suitable method to detect damage occurrences in composite materials using the FBG AE sensing system.

Figure 5. Comparison of shared portion of wavelet components between the undamaged case (0.1 J impact) and damaged case (5.0 J impact) detected by FBG sensors.

MONITORING OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS USING FBG SENSORS

The composite pressure vessels have diverse failure modes, and the failure in this structure causes a big problem in most cases. In this study, the application of FBG sensors to filament wound structures was investigated from all aspects, from the feasibility of the FBG sensors to the signal stability in harsh environments such as high pressure and cryogenic temperature[10].

Firstly, from the pressurization tests for strain monitoring of three different types of composite pressure vessels with embedded and attached FBG sensors, the design requirements of FBG sensors can be derived. They were the enhanced fabrication method for higher mechanical strength of FBG sensors, signal stability and exact alignment. After that, a composite/aluminum ring specimen and a Type III cryogenic propellant tank (Fig. 6) was fabricated with embedded FBG sensors to measure internal and external strains under the extreme conditions of large compression and cryogenic temperature (-150°C). In the ring specimen test, the thermal strains of the aluminum liner and the composite were measured, and the strain changes during the cyclic loading test were monitored. In the cryogenic propellant tank, the signal distortion was much severer, but the mechanical behaviours of each layer could be distinguished. Moreover, the delamination between helical and hoop layers was detected, and this supports the possible superiority of FBG sensors to the strain gauges.

Figure 6. Cryogenic composite tank filled with LN_2 and Strain changes during refrigeration.

In the next step, the novel algorithm for the signal distortion problem observed at low temperature was suggested, because the distorted reflection signals from embedded or attached FBG sensors could not be transferred to strain information. The center-of-mass algorithm (Fig. 7) calculated the approximated center wavelength that indicated the mean strain value from the distorted spectrum. The algorithm was analytically validated in axial strain gradient and transverse stress conditions. However, while the comparison between the real mean strains and the approximated center wavelength showed good coincidence in the strain gradient conditions, the birefringence effect caused by transverse stress left a certain amount of error in the measurement of axial strain.

Figure 7. Simulated FBG spectra under various strain gradient conditions.

As a one method for better sensors, the recently developed small-diameter FBG sensor (a core size of $6.5 \mu m$ and a cladding size of $40 \mu m$) was tested in a quasi-static indentation test on a composite plate. This test tried to show the difference between the normal-diameter and the small-diameter FBG sensors in the reflection spectra under nonuniform stress. As shown in Fig. 8, the small-diameter sensor was stronger to the nonuniform stress condition with its geometrical advantage.

Figure 8. Normalized spectra of the indentation test using a spherical indenter.

Finally, the small-diameter FBG sensor was embedded in a SCBA (self contained breathing apparatus) to monitor the thermal strain during refrigeration. The feasibility of embedded small-diameter FBG sensors in a composite vessel was tested, and the signal stability of FBG sensors in different conditions was compared. As a result, the small-diameter FBG sensors could successfully measure the strains during refrigeration to -150oC (Fig. 9). The small-diameter FBG sensors and acrylate coated normal-diameter FBG sensors could measure strains stably, while the uncoated FBG sensors showed spectral distortion and left errors in strain measurement.

Figure 9. Ingress/egress section of SD FBG sensors and Strain results from FBG sensors during refrigeration.

In this study, the structural health monitoring system using embedded FBG sensors was investigated in order to enable engineer to adopt the most adequate type of FBG sensors and monitoring techniques for the composite pressure vessels. The achieved results can contribute to establish the better structural health monitoring system for the composite structures in harsh environments.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, some applications for structural health monitoring using FBG sensors and some improvements for real applications were introduced. From the above several applications, some novel methods to overcome limitations of FBG sensors were proposed and devised. Through these kinds of trials and researches to overcome FBG sensor's disadvantages, the possibility of applications of FBG sensors to real structures can be more improved.

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